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Note: /ć/, /ž/ - palatal affricates (as opposed to alveo-palatal affricates /tʃ/, /dʒ/)

I. Phonotactics

- all vowels may occur in any position within a word
- no clusters of identical consonants: if this kind of cluster arises through morphological processes and assimilatory processes, one of the consonant is omitted: ex. od + dvojititi = odvojiti 'to separate'
- *cluster dental+affricates: dental is dropped
ex.: otac - oca 'father': NOM-GEN (instead of otca)
- clusters that are traditionally considered to occur at the end of a word: st, ft, zd, zd
- a word ending in any other cluster will generally have a fleeting a inserted before the final consonant

II. Phonological Processes

i. /r/ can become syllabic

- between two consonants (or a C and a sonorant): prst 'finger', krv 'blood'
- at the beginning of a word in front of a C: rt 'cape', rzati 'to neigh'
- at the boundary between a prefix and a C: zaržati 'to get rusty'

ii. Voicing Assimilation

- regressive
- when two consonants differing in voicing meet through derivational and inflectional processes

ex.: težak - teška 'heavy, masc - fem'
učiti 'to study' - udžbenik 'textbook'

- if the consonants have become identical: one is dropped

ex.: iz + stupiti = istupiti 'step out'

iii. Palatalization (alveo-palatal).

- /s/, /z/ > [ʃ], [ʒ] / _dʒ, tʃ, ʒ, ć, ĺ or ŋ

except /s/ and /z/ followed by /ŋ/ or /ħ/ that are root initial

- /k, g, x/ > [tʃ, ʒ, ʃ] / _e : in inflection, but not always - some suffixes do not trigger palatalization

ex.: radnik - radnitše 'worker: NOM-VOC'

- /k, g, x/ > [tʃ, ʒ, s] / _i : in the imperative of verbs with stems ending in a velar and in the nominative, dative, locative, instrumental of masculine plurals; in the dative and locative of feminine singulars

ex.: rekao - reši 'he said - say!'

- "jotation" (j- palatal glide): appears in the passive participle verbs with the infinitive stem ending in -i, in the present of verbs with the infinitive stem ending in -a and the first person singular present stem ending -(i)jem (except when in the infinitive stem /r/ or /v/ is in front of /a/), in the comparative of certain adjectives, in the instrumental of i-type nouns, in word formation

a) /s, z/ > [ʃ, ʒ] / _j

ex.: pisati 'to write' > pišem 'I write'

b) /t, d/ > [ć, ǰ] / _j

c) /k, g, x/ > [tʃ, ʒ, ʃ] / _j

ex.: dug 'long' - duži 'longer'

d) /l, n/ > [ħ, ŋ] / _j

ex.: dalek 'far' - daħi 'farther'

iv. Insertion of [ħ]

- appears in the passive participle verbs with the infinitive stem ending in -i, in the present of verbs with the infinitive stem ending in -a and the first person singular present stem ending -(i)jem (except when in the infinitive stem /r/ or /v/ is in front of /a/)

- added after labials

ex.: ljubiti 'to kiss' > ljubħen 'kissed'

v. Dropping of /t/

- omitted between s, z, š, ž and n, l or some other consonants (not mentioned which ones!)

ex.: bolestan 'ill' - bolesnik 'ill person' (instead of bolestnik)

- no dropping at prefix boundary

ex.: iz+tlatfjiti = istlatfjiti 'to oppress'

vi. Vowel Alternation

- sporadic and restricted to few words or a group adjective, no generally applying processes:

a) alternation I ~ o: at the end of a word or syllable

- all masculine singular active past participle: ex. radila - radio 'she worked - he worked'; and in the nouns derive from it radionica 'workshop'

- few adjectives in the masculine singular

- in adjectives and nouns with exceptions: posla - posao 'job:GEN - NOM/ACC'; but bola - bol 'pain:GEN - NOM/ACC'

- masculine nouns ugao 'corner', deo 'part', sto 'table', vo 'ox' and the feminine noun so 'salt' end in o in the nominative singular while [I] appears in the nominative plural and other cases: ex. sto NOM.SG - stolovi NOM.PL

- nouns ending in the suffix -lats, where the [I] is retained in the nominative singular and genitive plural but is replaced by [o] in all other instances, as [I] changes to [o] at the end of a syllable which precedes a syllable beginning with [ts], when the [I] is not final it is not replaced by the [o]

b) alternation a ~ ø ('moveable or fleeting a'): affects the final C-cluster (often includes sonorants) - separates stem final clusters especially in the NOM.SG and GEN.PL

- restricted to some nouns, adjectives, participles, pronouns in certain cases:

ex. kruška 'pear' - kruškaka 'pear.GEN.PL'

- frequent in loan words: ex. metar 'meter' - metri 'meter.PL'

- does not affect clusters: st, zd, ft, žd, šć, žž, consonant+ j-clusters

c) alternation o ~ e after /tʃ, dʒ, ʃ, ʒ, ć, ž, j, ʎ, ŋ, ts, ft, ʒd/ and sometimes /r/

- applies in neuter and masculine declension, ex.: kraľ 'king' - kraľem

(*kraľom)

- in feminine declension it is applied only in the vocative sg of most nouns with the suffix ica

c) alternation /ije/ - /je/ - /e/ - /i/ in the (i)jekavian pronunciation: ije in long syllables, je in short syllables, i in front of o which is the alternant of I, e in short syllables after a consonant and a r

III. Stem formation - Infix

- monosyllabic nouns of the a-declension (masculine) get the infix -ov- (-ev- after palatals) in front of the plural ending, but here are exceptions
 - some disyllabic nouns with the moveable a also get the infix -ov-
- ex. mozak 'brain', mozga GEN.SG, mozgovi NOM.PL

IV. Stress

4 accents: short falling (˘), long falling (˘̄), short rising (ˆ), long rising (ˆ̄)
 placement and contour can alternate within the paradigm of a word:
 ex.: ˘`mena 'name.GEN.SG' ; imèna 'NOM.SG' ; iménā 'GEN.PL'

- the accent on polysyllables is never placed on the last syllable
 - the falling accent appears on monosyllables
 - the falling accent appears on polysyllables only on the first syllable
 - the rising accent cannot appear on monosyllables
 - the rising accent in polysyllables can appear on all syllables except the last
 - pro- (Prepositions, Negation) or enclitics have no accented syllable of their own
 - exceptions:
 - falling accent can jump onto proclitics becoming the short rising or short falling accent
 - if the preposition is bi- or trisyllabic , the stress will fall on the last syllable if it is a rising accent, or on the first syllable if it is a falling accent
- ex.: trè`bā 'he / she needs' - nè`trebā 'he / she doesn't need'
- post accentual length (˘̄) is notated
- ex.: pò`plava 'flood.NOM.SG' vs. pò`plāvā GEN.PL

V. Clitics

Enclitics

- order of enclitics in the sentence is strictly fixed (in contrast to a generally flexible word order): grouped in the second position in the sentence (Wackernagel) order (presence is not obligatory):
 - interrogative enclitic li (marker of yes/no-question)
 - verbal enclitics: auxiliary verbs used in forming various tenses (/je/ is not a verbal enclitic in this position)
 - pronominal enclitics: dative - genitive - accusative
 - enclitic reflexive pronoun se
 - verbal enclitic je (3.SG.PRS of auxiliary biti 'to be'): when it follows enclitic reflexive pronoun se, it is generally omitted
 - the second position can be the position after the first constituent or after the first word of the first constituent
- ex.: moj-a majk-a je jutfer dofl-a

my-NOM.FEM.SG mother-NOM.FEM.SG be.AUX.3.SG yesterday
 arrive.PTCP.FEM.SG
 moj-a je majk-a jutfer dofl-a
 my-NOM.FEM.SG be.AUX.3.SG mother-NOM.FEM.SG yesterday
 arrive.PTCP.FEM.SG

'My mother arrived yesterday'

- if the first constituent is relatively long, then the enclitic can exceptionally follow the second constituent (or the first word of the second constituent)

ex. moj-a prijateljic-a koj-a studira
 u Madrid-u jutfer je dofl-a
 my-NOM.FEM.SG friend-NOM.FEM.SG which-NOM.FEM.SG study.PRS.3.SG
 in Madrid-LOC.MASC.SG yesterday be.AUX.3.SG arrive.PTCP-FEM.SG

'My friend who is studying in Madrid arrived yesterday.'

- personal pronoun have full or enclitic form in the GEN, DAT, ACC
 - enclitic forms are not stressed
- reflexive pronoun does not have the enclitic form in GEN
- full forms of pronouns are obligatory after prepositions, in contrasting, if they are placed sentence-initially (for emphasis)

- auxiliaries:

- all are enclitics and follow the enclitic order
- indicate person and number, while the main verb they accompany will, depending on the tense, generally only express number
- when the negative past tense is used, the AUX is no longer considered an enclitic and can take first position in the sentence

Proclitics

- sentence negation is expressed by negating a finite verb by means of the proclitic ne 'noz':

- no information about phonological behavior

ex.: Oni ne studira-ju
 they.NOM not study -PRS.3.PL
 'They are not studying'

- the same entity 'ne' is used in constituent negation and in negation of a subordinated sentences: 'ne' is placed before

ex.: Mark-o je narutjio ne sok, nego piv-o
 Marko-NOM.MASC.SG be.AUX.3.SG order.PTCP

- prepositions act as proclitics in that they do not normally carry stress, but there are instances (see Stress chapter)